

The Holistic Perspective of the Lutheran Chorale as an Integrating Factor of the Christian Faith

Cristian Caraman, PhD

'Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute of Bucharest, Romania
Baptist Theological Institute, Bucharest, Romania
caramancm@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT: Music is the art which demonstrated that the rapprochement of people (in spite of religious differences from a dogmatic and cultic perspective), is necessary and feasible, as long as the superior idea of faith exists as a vital guiding principle that has the purpose of combating the essential evil. Music created a path through which a dialog was started between the main religious orientations—Catholic, Orthodox and Protestant. Humanity had been struggling to reach a superior level of affirmation of its ideals, and Christianity, of any form, had been helping in its efforts to overcome such struggles. For, of course, as music builds on the principle of universal harmony, our deeds follow suit. The beginnings of the Protestant music in the Europe of the 14th–16th centuries are related to the spiritual manifestations necessary for the shaping of the new religious and, first of all, to the great stature of Martin Luther and the other representatives of the Reformation. Over time, the shedding of values and routines had established certain hierarchies, but the creation of new musical genera during the Renaissance appears useful in building a Protestant music repertoire. The musical core is—and this argument is that the model resists the test of history—the Lutheran chorus, which will become more and more defined in its manifold manifesto. It is worth appreciating the details of the types of Choral, Anthem, Hymn, Cantata and Passion. The holistic perspective of the Lutheran chorus culminates with Bach, which in turn, makes the Lutheran spiritual model more clearly understood,

but also has lasting consequences in classicism, romanticism, to the creation of 20th-century composers.

KEY WORDS: Lutheran Chorale, Protestant Music, Holistic, Christianity, Reformation

The role of the Lutheran chorale in music

The Lutheran Chorale created by Martin Luther and developed harmonically by the Wittenberg musicians during the Protestant Reformation, played a double role by stimulating the musical creativity and to encourage the worship of God by the congregation.

The spiritual significance of the chorale was established by Martin Luther, which wanted to encourage the congregation to develop a personal relationship with God. Luther also believed that the church music was responsible to bring people to church every Sunday, for the purpose of worship.

The most important accomplishment of Luther's reformation of the sixteenth century was the integration of congregational singing within the worship service of the Lutheran church. "After theology I give music the highest place and highest honor."¹ In order to encourage the participation of the believers within the liturgy, Martin Luther created the chorale which was very accessible to the congregation, but was able to transmit profound theological truths. The Lutheran Chorale has a simple melodic line and the text is in German. In order to encourage the understanding of theological texts and to make it easier for the people in the congregation, the text was always in German. Luther replaced the traditional liturgical language, which was Latin, with German. Through the chorale, Luther made his wish come true by allowing the German people to express their beliefs and worship in their native tongue. The German language, full of consonants, needed a particular musical style, in contrast with Latin, which is rich in vowels. The liturgical music, composed on Latin texts was characterized by long phrases, with free rhythms where the vowels were held for long periods of time. The German Chorale had a more syllabic style with less melisma's. In

the beginning, during the liturgy, the chorales were unaccompanied and were sung in a monodic style.

Also, in order for the chorales to be sung by untrained voices, due to its vocalic text, the melodies were characterized by very few interval jumps. The creation of the Lutheran Churches during the sixteenth century, led to the need of new liturgical music to serve the Lutheran ideology. The purpose of such new music was to create and transmit the subtle and profound Lutheran theology. The Lutheran composers then used old melodies in combination with new melodic lines. The Lutheran Chorale developed very rapidly in the sixteenth century, by using sacred and non-religious music. The early chorales from the Contrafact period, used well known texts, which were added to Gregorian melodies. The official Latin hymns, the religious songs of the Meistersinger and the folk German songs. A good example of the relation between the Gregorian Chant and the Lutheran Chorale is Luther's Chorale *All Ehr' und Lob soll Gottes sein* (All Glory, Laud, and Praise Be Given), which was based on the Gregorian melody *Gloria tempore paschali*.² Lutherans have often adopted folk German songs and modified them to religious texts. One such piece is *Gott der Vater won uns bei* (God the Father with Us Be).³ Most Lutherans used non-religious songs in their liturgy, by replacing the original text with a spiritual one. One such example is, *Ich komm aus fremden Landen her* (I come from foreign lands), with a new text which turned the song into the well-known chorale, *Vom Himmel kam der Engel Schar* (From Heaven the Angel Troop Came Near).⁴

One example of such chorale is *O Welt, ich muss dich lassen* („O World, I now must leave thee”), which is a contrafact of the famous secular song *Innsbruck, ich muss dich lassen* by Heinrich Isaac (Innsbruck, I Now Must Leave Thee).⁵ Based on familiar ideas of the time, most Lutheran text had double meaning, which is lost to today's congregations. The fundamental tradition was the inspiration for Johann Sebastian Bach's compositions, where he used the juxtaposition of familiar melodies to religious texts. In spite of this method of music creation of the sixteenth century, a lot of Lutheran composers used original compositions and texts for their chorales. It is important to mention that the texts and melodies for new chorales were usually written by the same person. This method was used to

create a homogenous symbiotic relationship between text and music. From the very beginning the Lutheran Chorale was a combination of music and theological concepts, which were impossible to separate.

The harmonized Chorales

The need for harmonized chorales in the Lutheran Church grew with time and by the end of the sixteenth century many chorales were already harmonized. The first harmonized chorales appeared in 1524, and were composed by the Lutheran composer Johann Walter. Johann Walter kept all the original rhythmical verse of the cantus firmus, but placed the cantus firmus in the tenor voice, much like the majority of the Renaissance music. The untrained believers had a major problem when hearing the melody in the lower voice, hence the Lucas Osiander, moved the melody to the higher voice. This stylistic change allowed the congregation to learn the chorales a lot easier. Most harmonized chorales of the sixteenth century were modal, and in the beginning of the seventeenth century Hans Leo Hassler published chorale arrangements which were more tonal in their harmonic structure. Other composers, such as Michael Praetorius and Johann Balthasar Koenig, contributed with the introduction of instruments. J. S. Bach harmonized more than 400 Lutheran chorales, with the sole purpose of being used during the liturgy. He also incorporated various chorales in his cantatas, oratorios and passions. J.S. Bach's use of the chorale in his own compositions was related to his wish to bring the Lutheran theology and ideology to all.

Bach's ability to take Lutheran melodies and infuse them with new concepts by new harmonic structures brought the Chorale to the perfection it was originally imagined to be. Bach's knowledge of harmony allowed him to perfect this genre and give more musical meaning to his spiritual beliefs. One such example is the harmonization of *Ein' feste Burg ist unser Gott* (A Mighty Fortress Is Our God),⁶ where Bach uses close harmonic intervals to create the feeling of a fortified wall, which cannot be penetrated, or demolished. Bach also uses the fermata to indicate the ending of textual phrases.

The motet chorale

The motet chorale is a composition „in a polyphonic style, in one or two parts, based on a German melody of a Chorale.”⁷ In the beginning, the motet chorale was interpreted a cappella, and later with various instruments, or the organ replaced one or more voices. One of these chorale motets is *Komm, Heiliger Geist, Herre Gott*, no. 108, written as a canon by Arnold von Bruck. The *choral-motet*, developed with a four partial harmonization, initially modeled after the work of Dutch composers of the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. This model of chorale-motet is characterized by rhythmic and melodic imitations, smooth cadenzas, polyphonic textures, canon techniques, and equality between voices. Johann Walter arranged some of those chorales in a motet style before 1524, and his compositions used *cantus firmus* in the tenor voice. The other voices, supported the cantus firmus in a polyphonic style. Hans Leo Hassler introduced Venetian polyphonic elements. In his works, all the voices were changed in a mirror type dialogue. This writing style brought balance to all voices and essentially eliminated the cantus firmus line. Michael Praetorius also included fugal and madrigal elements in the choral-motet compositions to attain a better balance amongst the voices. He also made use of complex polyphonic parts and a freer melodic line. However, the most important contribution to the choral-motet was the introduction of accompaniment instruments. Up until J.S. Bach the typical motet made use of continuo instruments. The texts for all his works were based on biblical passages. Bach’s ability to infuse his works with his genius is clearly seen in his polyphonic discourse of the Lutheran Chorales. *Fantasia super Ich ruf zu Dir, Herr Jesu Christ* by Samuel Scheidt and *Nun Komm, der Heiden Heiland* by J. S. Bach are very good examples of significant chorale-motets composed during his life. Even though he made use of the traditional form of the style, he infused his works with more contrast and very well established biblical texts. One of the most original of all his motets is, *Jesu, meine Freude*. In this work, Bach uses cantus firmus almost like a variation on themes. The melody of the chorale comes back eleven times throughout the work and every time is just slightly

different. Bach is probably the first composer to incorporate this style of variations in a vocal polyphonic genre. Stylistic characteristic of Bach's motet-chorale includes short syllables, a small number of long notes, repetitions and many high notes. Also, he applies ornamental discourses and instruments for each voice.

Bach's contribution to the Lutheran Chorale

Bach's Lutheran faith began in his early childhood and developed during his school years, where the Bible, catechism and the religious hymns were the most important educational tools. His role of church organist and boy soprano allowed him to become very familiar with the chorale texts and its melodies.

During his school years, Bach learned about the spiritual importance of the chorale. He was a frequent attendee of his local Lutheran Church, where his father was the music director. Bach learned about the Bible, participated in congregational singing and learned the Lutheran doctrine. These formative years allowed him to develop a religious base, which he used later in life by writing music for worshipping God.

Bach wanted to create church music that was well organized and for the glory of God. He frequently used chorale texts, which were essential to the Lutheran church service. Even though, when composed, many melodies were composed in a matter that represented the clarity of the biblical message, he also included some of his smaller works within larger compositions. He always encouraged the congregational singing and the worship of God. In his instrumental works, he utilized the chorale, by exploiting the many ways of musical and literary expression.

The cantatas⁸ and the passions⁹ that he composed represent the sum of his entire artistic experience, showing his great talent. Also, his melodies could be found inserted in his instrumental works, or more frequently in cantatas and oratorios. The purpose of this intertwining was to allow the listener to worship God. In this musical representation, Bach presents the suffering of Christ and wanted to truly express the significance of Christ's sacrifice.

One example of such work is *Matthäus Passion*, which contains a melody in the soprano part, of which text expresses the prayer and the painful sound of a multitude of people worshiping God. It is very possible that Bach original thought was to have the congregation participate, by singing during the first movement of the Passion. This way, even though the music was very ornamented and complex, the listeners could easily listen and appreciate the message of the text. Due to the combinations full of significance of the texts and music, Bach's listeners were inspired to worship and praise God. A common fact in Bach's cantatas is the use of instruments, especially for the various harmonies used, while the soloist interprets a biblical, or poetic text. It is very important to notice the way Bach combines the texts with the music, to create profound understanding of the Lutheran doctrine. The organ chorales are elaborated musical works, which necessitate virtuosic interpretation, but are appropriate for the church service as well. These works represent some of the most important works ever composed by Bach. These chorales use entire chorales, or parts of chorales, composed for the purpose of introducing the congregation to a new type of chorale. All of these works portray the textual and liturgical significance, while exploiting the virtuosic nature of playing the organ. Some of these works include the *chorale-motet*¹⁰ form, *chorale-fantasia* and *chorale-fughetta*.

The fughetta style uses imitation in the motet style, without the use of the cantus firmus. Also, there are organ chorales which make extensive use of variations and preludes. The variations are in a Partita style, and Bach was fascinated by this for at the end of his career. These works are usually used as interludes, between various verses of the chorale. *Overture-chorale* has two versions, short and long. Some of the techniques used for these Overture-chorales, are putting the melody in the alto voice, creating a fantasy-chorale form, which ornamented the composition. The short overtures are found in the book *Orgel-Büchlein*. Long overtures include cantus firmus melodies, trios, and the ritornello form. In the *hymn-chorale* (contra punctum simplex), we find simple harmonization of four to five voices, where the chorale melody (cantus firmus) extends for the entire duration of the work, in one single voice. This is called the uninterrupted form.¹¹ Cantus firmus is usually found in the soprano

voice, while the lower voices don't mirror, or replicate each other. The lower voices support the main voice and borrow musical material from the cantus firmus. During his life, Bach was capable to express his musical genius and to bring up the most important aspects of Lutheranism, through his compositions. He was also very successful in perfecting genres, other composers brought to light.

Conclusions

The Lutheran chorale flows seamlessly in the history of universal music, representing different styles and developing amazing artistic value to the Christian musical world. The Lutheran music calls for profound spiritual meditation and deals with the human spiritual condition. Protestant music, in general, has its well-defined place within the cultural and universal artistic expression. The Lutheran chorale, alongside the Cantata and Oratorio, represent the pillars of protestant music. The holistic perspective of the Lutheran chorale found its uses in philosophy, culture, history, sociology and last, but not least, in musicology.

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NOTES

¹ Friedrich Blume, *Protestant Church Music a History*, Friedtich Blume in collaboration with Ludwig Finscher, Georg Feder, Adam Adrio, Walter Blankenburg, Torben Schousboe, Robert Stevenson, and Watkins Shaw, Foreword by Paul Henry Lang (New York: W. W. Norton & Company, Inc., 1974), 10.

² Ulrich S. Leupold, *Luther's Works, vol. 53, Liturgy and Hymns* (Philadelphia: Concordia Publishing House, 1965), 209. *All Ehr und Lob soll Gottes sein - Hymnary.org*, site: https://hymnary.org/text/all_ehr_und_lob_soll_gottes_sein, (Accessed February 2, 2018).

³ *Ibid.*, 208, 269; Blume, *Protestant Church Music a History*, 21; *Gott der Vater wohn' uns bei - Lutheran Hymnal*, site: www.lutheran-hymnal.com/german/tlh247g.htm, (Accessed February 2, 2018).

⁴ Blume, 208; *Vom Himmel kam der Engel Schar - Wikipedia*, site: https://de.wikipedia.org/.../Vom_Himmel_kam_der_Engel_S..., (Accessed February 2, 2018).

⁵ Blume, 33; *O Welt, ich muß dich lassen*, site: www.mab.jp/musictex/score_lib/hi_owelt.pdf, (Accessed February 2, 2018).

⁶ *Ein feste Burg ist unser Gott - Wikipedia*, site: https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ein_feste_Burg_ist_unser_Gott, (Accessed February 2, 2018).

⁷ Cristian Caraman, *Genuri ale Muzicii Protestante* (București: Editura Universității Naționale de Muzică, 2011), 79.

⁸ Cantata (Germ.: *Kantate*; Ital.; Fr. *Cantate*) is a vocal composition with an instrumental accompaniment, typically in several movements, often involving a choir. Ibid, 118; see also DEXI-*Dicționar Explicativ Ilustrat al Limbii Române*, Chișinău: Editura ARC & GUNIVAS, 2007; Alison Latham, *The Oxford Companion to MUSIC* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2002), 202, 203.

⁹ Passion (music) In Christian music a Passion is a setting of the Passion of Christ. Liturgically most Passions were intended to be performed as part of church services in the Holy Week. As a form, the Passion stands between biblical declamatory text and Oratorio. Passion was performed mostly in the German speaking countries after 1600. The theological base of the Protestant Passion was modeled after *Theologia Crucis* written by Martin Luther. Ibid., 140, 152; Latham, *The Oxford Companion to Music*, 933, 934; DEXI - *Dicționar Explicativ Ilustrat al Limbii Române*, 2007.

¹⁰ There are multiple forms of the protestant chorale, such as: chorale-cantata, chorale-concert, chorale-fantasy, chorale-fugue, chorale-ricercar, chorale-monody, chorale-motet, chorale for organ, chorale-prelude, chorale-psalm, chorale-variation, chorale-suite, chorale-symphony, chorale-lied, chorale-aria, chorale-hymn, trio-chorale, chorale-Mass. Caraman, *Genuri ale Muzicii Protestante*, 60-92.

¹¹ Ibid., 93.